

About the PA ratio for Urban Footprint

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Summary

Urban fragmentation is a major challenge of sustainable urban planning. This article analyzes urban patches based on Urban Atlas 2018, covering 788 Functional Urban Areas (FUAs) 2018. Our linear regression models identify the ‘shape-index’ of the urban patches across the FUAs to identify the most pertinent spatial analysis to understand the complexity of cities. Furthermore, we favor estimated coefficients over averages, providing a better understanding of the ‘shape-index’ metric. Decision makers and researchers can use this geodatabase to guide future development towards better planning for the shape of our cities.

KEYWORDS: fragmentation, landscape, urban, perimeter area ratio, shape-index

1 Introduction

Urban development significantly impacts the natural environment by fragmenting natural areas (EEA. and FOEN., 2016), affecting quality of life and social cohesion. Thus, reducing urban fragmentation is a central objective of sustainable urban planning, aiming to create a balance ”between” natural and urban environments. In this study, we focus only on urban areas measured by the perimeter-to-area ratio.

The P/A ratio is a common metric used to analyse the structure of landscapes in ecology from an aerial perspective. In landscape ecology terms (McGarigal and Marks, 1995), a landscape is ‘an area of land containing a mosaic of patches’. In practice, a patch is any polygon, of any shape, with a single land use category. Measuring the complexity of patches of artificial land and their arrangement within a particular urban region, i.e. the complexity of a physical urban footprint, is key to understanding the impact of urbanisation patterns and their change on ecological habitats and on the functioning of the city itself. The P/A ratio is a simple and intuitive indicator of shape complexity. When the square root of the area is used as denominator, this complexity indicator is made independent of the size (area) of the object (patch) (Feder, 1988; McGarigal and Marks, 1995) and sometimes called ‘shape-index’.

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Our goal is to address those issues head-on by assessing the robustness of the ‘shape-index’ to the definition of patches and to the aggregation methods. We suggest that instead of using arithmetic mean averages, we should look at the entire relationship between perimeter and square root of the area and how the slope of this relationship changes as urban patches are added in order of area. More specifically, we explore how to quantify the complexity of urban areas in all European cities.

1.1 Urban P/A ratio

In urban planning, a simple uniform shape is favorable, indicating a compact city (Alphan, 2021), while a complex shape signals high fragmentation. Without indicating whether the link between the P/A ratio and urban areas is relevant or significant, it is a fact that this index is commonly used (Williams et al., 2005; Irwin and Bockstael, 2007; Salmanmahiny et al., 2014; Le Texier et al., 2024), but the effect of the index is still unclear. Eventually, whether a complex urban form is good or bad is difficult to say, especially since the literature provides surprisingly little comparable measurements of the shape of cities based on these basic characteristics (perimeter and area) measured over their basic units, i.e. urban patches. There are no agreed reference values with which we can confront case studies, and more importantly, the field lacks clarity in defining the patches that make up an urban footprint and lacks a unified methodology to aggregate the description of the patch level up to the urban region level (Dewan et al., 2012; Triantakonstantis and Stathakis, 2015).

2 Method

This study analyses urban patches based on Urban Atlas 2018 (Copernicus), covering 785 functional urban areas (FUAs) in Europe. We classified 23 land cover categories into 2 classes to create the urban footprint with $u = 1$ for urban and $u = 0$ otherwise. As a measure for each city, urban patches are defined by 3 spatial analyses i , j and g as in Figure 1 to test the robustness s as the ‘shape-index’.

Figure 1: Definition of the element patches for i , j , and g

- case i : using original patches without the road with the mean \bar{s}_i or in estimated form \hat{s}_i
- case j : using merging patches that touch each other after a road neighboring cell analysis

with the mean \bar{s}_j or in estimated form \hat{s}_j and without outliers define by the Cook's Distance $\hat{s}_{j.c}$

- case g : all patches of the case j are merged into a single patch, by construction, there is one value per city: s_g

Figure 2: Linear regression applies to urban patches by j analysis and $j.c$ in Montpellier - with s_{square} as the simplest reference value

The problem is that such an averaging ignores the statistical distribution of the shape index s within each city and forces a mean constant relation between the perimeter and area of each elementary unit. We propose to contrast those means to the slopes directly estimated from elementary perimeters and areas in both the i and j cases. Estimate it with a linear regression without an intercept, i.e. (1) for j and $j.c$ as the example of Montpellier in Figure 2. For better visual understanding, we show the map of all urban patches as shown Figure 3.

$$p_j = \hat{s}_j \sqrt{a_j} \quad (1)$$

Nevertheless, those fits are highly influenced by outlying values with the case j , we make those estimates after removing outliers, but we further demonstrated that a single estimated 'shape-index' is insufficient. Therefore, we compute a profile of estimations for subsets of increasing size along the area dimension ranging from the initial values to the maximum as in Figure 4.

Figure 3: Mapping of the analysis j and $j.c$ of all urban patches of Montpellier with the shape index values and the outliers shape-index $s_{j,o}$

Figure 4: Estimated shape index calculated for the share of total surface values from 0.01 to 1

3 Results

The results provide quantitative maps and charts to identify the most complex cities in all European cities. We find that analysis j , which reclassifies and aggregates urban patches, is more accurate than using the original data and provides a better representation of reality, allowing for more effective comparisons between cities. The $j.c$, which provided a good adjustment to fit the observed values, allows us to examine rural complexity by excluding outliers defined as the urban central core. The estimated coefficient showed that the urban patch across Europe has a mean of 11.03 which is a good indicator of world cities. Our results show that cities with more developed secondary complex urban bodies are more fragmented and have higher contact with the rural environment. Complex urban patches are located together, as seen in Portugal around Porto, Belgium, Netherlands, and England, whereas simple urban patches are common in Spain, Turkey, Germany, and Bulgaria as shown in Figure 5. This information can guide decision-makers towards a balanced urban development.

Providing readers or users with the possibility to obtain the level of complexity depends on the profile as in Figure 4, which depends on the spatial consideration that we can take into account within the analysis. The range of 0.05 to 0.50 is mainly the rural environment and the small isolated patches that are crucial for ecological studies. And higher than 0.50 are more indicative of the general shape of the cities, which are the large patches. Notably, by looking at such profiles, we can understand the difference between the role of urban core patches and secondary patches that are more peripheral, often less complex, and smaller. We think our novel approach is an important step towards a better understanding of the impact of more fragmented or complex urban footprints.

4 Conclusion

Future planning strategies are required to address questions related to land fragmentation. Linear regression models have enabled us to identify the most pertinent patch definition to understand the complexity of cities. Although case i is still used in the literature, it does not accurately represent the actual trend of the city's shape. Focusing on the case j helps us understand the need to remove outliers to obtain a model that fits the observational values and quantifies urban complexity. The selected statistical modeling $j.c$ showed considerable variations and a spatial heterogeneity of the complexity across Europe. In addition, by systematically examining the urban footprint of 785 urban regions of different sizes, we provide a set of reference values and profiles that can be used for comparative studies at different scales and different stages of urban growth.

Figure 5: Mapping of the estimate coefficient $\hat{s}_{j,c}$

5 Biography

Graduated with a Master's in Mapping and Environmental Management from the University of Nantes. Léandre is currently a doctoral researcher focusing on urban development, specifically exploring fragmentation across Europe depending on the shape complexity of urban patches.

Geoffrey Caruso is Professor for urban analysis and modelling at the University of Luxembourg since 2007. He employs various methodological trajectories of urban science, from GIS and applied spatial statistics to landuse transport interactions and theoretical agent-based models, in order to contribute understanding of urban forms, green space, or residential and transport decisions.

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